

A Study on Job Satisfaction of Women Teachers of Private Schools in Periyakulam Town

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Abstract

Job satisfaction is one factor that will ensure class performance and productivity of schools. The teachers would get interested to teach their students effectively when they are satisfied with their jobs. Like India, other countries in the world are trying to improve their quality of education, so that it meets the demand of globalization. Teachers would perform to maximum capacity, only if they are satisfied with their jobs. So, job satisfaction is an important phenomena in every sector especially in the teaching profession. This study aims to analysis the job satisfaction of women teachers, perception towards job satisfaction, organizational climate and also job involvement of women teachers of private schools in periyakulam town.

Introduction

Job satisfaction is an affective reaction to an individual's work situation, and has been described as a positive emotional response resulting from appraisal of one's job. It is the function of the degree to which one's needs can be satisfied and operationalised as a discrepancy between 'how much is there now' and 'how much there should be'. One of the aspects that can lead to dissatisfaction is one's attitude towards one's job. Job attitude can be defined as an overall feeling about one's job or career or in terms of specific facets of the job or career (e.g. compensation, autonomy, coworkers) and can be related to specific outcomes, such as productivity.

Statement of the Problem

Teacher's job satisfaction is not only important to the teachers but also important to the students. Teachers retention, commitment can be predicted by job satisfaction(Shann 2001). This shows that job satisfaction is important for school teachers.

Objectives of the Study

1. To measure the level of satisfaction of teachers in Private Schools.

2. To compare the job satisfaction of the school teachers with respect to their school management.
3. To undertake a study of female teachers regarding their job satisfaction.

Review of Literature

Job satisfaction is one of the most widely researched subject. Job satisfaction acts as a moderator for generating the relationship between working conditions and individual outcomes (Dorman and Zapf,2001).Ahmed, Raheem , and Jamal(2003) conducted a study on job satisfaction of 236 teachers in secondary school. It was observed that the female teachers are highly satisfied when compared to the male teachers. The teachers working in the government school showed higher satisfaction than the teachers working in the private schools.

Gupta and Sahu/(2009) conducted a study on job satisfaction.It deals with the relationship of job satisfaction with the organizational stress and place of control on vocational teachers.The results revealed that there is no significant gender difference between organizational stress and place of control on vocational school teachers.

Noll(2004) examined the factors which affect the job satisfaction of the teachers. It was observed that the motivation, teachers relationship with the administration and working environment were the factors that affect the job satisfaction of the teachers.

Dr. A. Kannan and D.Jenita Vol. 7 (2019) pp. 53-59 Shanlax International journal of commerce conducted “A Study on job satisfaction of women employees of private sector banks in Ramanathapuram town”. The study aims to measure the level of study job satisfaction, job involvement and organizational climate of women employees in banking sector.

Scope of the Study

This study is emphasized on the job satisfaction of women teachers of private schools in periyakulam town.

Area of the Study

The school taken for this study is Seventhday advenstic Matric Higher Secondary School,St. Anne’s Matric Higher Secondary School, Victory Matric Higher Secondary School,KAS Matriculation School, Jayaraj Chelladurai Matriculation School and Presidency Primary and Nursery School.

Methodology and Research Design

The present study is empirical. The questionnaire method is adopted as the instrument of collecting data directly from 120 women employees in periyakulam town, through random sampling technique. The primary data collected directly by the researcher and secondary data were collected from various books journals, magazines , websites and so on.

The Period of the Study

The period of study is confined to about six months i.e., from september 2018 to february 2019.

Data Collection and Analysis of Data

The present study covers the job satisfaction among the women teachers. Information and data have been extricated from questionnaire. The tool used for this study is like average and percentage analysis.

Limitation of the Study

Due to time and cost constraints, the study area covered only perikulam town and the result of the study is confined only to perikulam town. The sample size is 120 only which may not be sufficient to conclude the accurate response

Results and Analysis

In association to one's employing career, age plays an important factor. This is especially so in association with employee job satisfaction, which increases with increase in age.

Table 1 Age-wise classification

Sl.No.	Age-wise classification	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 25 years	10	08
2	26-35 years	70	58
3	36-45 years	15	13
4	Above 45 years	25	21
	Total	120	100

Agewise classification of the respondents reveals that 66% of teachers are young, that is in the age group of 35 and below and 13% respondents are middle aged(between 36 to 45 years). Other teachers are older (46 and above).

Literature shows that with a growth in the level of one's schooling, the level of dissatisfaction increases. Teachers motivation is important if they have to remain in the profession and it is also found that motivated teachers have higher job satisfaction.

Table 2 Education-wise classification

Sl.No.	Education-wise classification	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Diploma	30	25
2	U.G	37	31
3	P. G	50	42
4	Others	03	02
	Total	120	100

The respondents were categorized into four groups depending on educational qualification -Diploma, Bachelor's and Master's degree and others,other includes M.Phil and also Ph.D. The results showed that 31 percent of respondents possessed Bachelor's degree. 42 percent of respondents had Master's degree in education and 25 percent had diplomas while only 2 percent of respondents belongs others category.

Table 3 Years of Teaching Experience

Sl. No.	Years of Teaching Experience	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Below 5 years	70	58
2	6 to 10 years	30	25
3	More than 10 years	20	17
	Total	120	100

With respect to the teaching experience, it shows that majority of the teachers had been in their station of work from below 5 years(58 percent). 25 percent have teaching experience of six to ten years and remaining 17 percent had experience of more than years. Highly experienced teachers had high job satisfaction.

Table 4 Marital Status-wise classification

Sl. No.	Marital Status-wise classification	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Single	30	25
2	Married	90	75
	Total	120	100

Demographic details on marital status shows that majority of the respondents are married women(75%) and probably had families to take care of, while 25% of the teachers were still single.

Perception Towards Job Satisfaction of Women Teachers

The researcher has gathered the details from the women employees of Private sector to measure the level of job satisfaction. For this purpose overall opinion of the respondents are gathered by using. The statements and the score is obtained through relative scale values. Then on the basis of the score the job satisfaction level is measured and the same is presented in the following table.

Table 5 Perception towards job satisfaction among women employees

Sl. No.	Job satisfaction	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Highly satisfied	38	32
2	Moderately satisfied	50	42
3	Dissatisfied	32	26
	Total	120	100

It is clear from the above table 5 that out of 120 respondents interviewed 38 respondents have expressed that they are highly satisfied towards their job, 50 respondents are moderately satisfied towards their job and the remaining 32 respondents are dissatisfaction with their job. It is found that, majority of the private schools they are satisfied with their job is a welcoming feature.

Job Involvement of the Respondents

The statement and the score is obtained through relative scale value. Then on the basis of the score the job involvement level is measured and the same presented in the following table.

Table 6 Level of job involvement of women employees

Sl. No.	Job Involvement	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Highly level	37	31
2	Moderate level	44	37
3	Low level	39	32
	Total	120	100

The above table 6 clearly shows that, 44 respondents are having moderate involvement 37 respondents are having a high involvement and the remaining 39 respondents are having low level of involvement in their job. It is found that most of the women employees are having involvement in their jobs in private schools in the study area.

Perception Towards Organisation Climate

The Researcher has gathered the details from the respondents about their organizational climate under different dimensions like professional help, formalization, organization risk tasking, standardization, people organization, centralization, formulization communication, welfare concern. Therefore eight aspects are analysed with statement and the score is obtained. The results are presented in the following table.

Table 7 Perception towards Organization Climate

Sl. No.	Job Satisfaction	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Good	40	33
2	Moderate	53	44
3	Poor	27	23
	Total	120	100

The above table 7 shows that, 44 percent women teachers are having moderate perception with their organizational climate , 33 percent of the respondents having good perception towards their organizational climate and the remaining 23 percent of the respondents are having poor perception towards organizational climate. It is found that most of the repondents are having moderate perception towards their organizational climate of theprivate schools in the study are is motivating the women teachers to do their better performance in their concerned job.

Suggestions

A detailed analysis of job satisfaction of women teachers of the schools has been made and researcher has offered the following suggestions for the better improvement of the women teachers of private schools in periyakulam town

1. The women teachers in private schools are more concerned with relationships of other teachers. The friendly and supportive colleagues lead to increase job satisfaction in schools.
2. Appointment of additional staff is necessary in schools to reduce the workload of the teachers in private schools
3. Good amount of concessions, incentives and encouragement may also provide to the women teachers. This will go a long way to improve the morale of the women teachers.

Conclusion

Thus, the study concludes that organisational support towards teachers in enhancing jobsatisfaction is very important. All efforts should be taken to improve the job satisfaction ofteachers. Having inferred from this study that freedom at workplace is the most sought after characteristic of job satisfaction, organisation should create self motivated teams at school. Some suggestions towards achieving job satisfaction are self developmental opportunities, short termcourses, seminars, workshops, high appreciation and rewards for commendable work are some of the ways in which job satisfaction can be improved.

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